

Effect of spray volume (0.75 kg a.i./ha) on mortality of brown planthoppers. IRRI insectary, 1980.

Insecticide and volume (liters/ha)	Mortality ^a (%)				
	1 DAT	5 DAT	10 DAT	15 DAT	20 DAT
Carbofuran 12 F					
1000	100 a	98 a	90 a	62 a	20 a
500	100 a	99 a	92 a	68 a	27 a
250	94 a	36 b	14 b	9 b	0 b
Perthane 45 EC					
1000	100 a	98 a	41 a	16 ab	2 a
500	98 a	84 a	39 a	30 a	8 a
250	100 a	93 a	39 a	7 b	0 a
Monocrotophos 30 EC					
1000	94 ab	32 a	10 a	7 a	2 a
500	95 a	28 a	7 a	3 a	2 a
250	83 b	26 a	0 a	2 a	0 a
UC54229 100 Tech.					
1000	99 a	100 a	91 a	55 a	25 a
500	100 a	99 a	82 a	42 ab	9 a
250	98 a	82 b	58 b	23 b	5 a

^aAdjusted using Abbott's formula. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DAT = days after treatment.

Mortality for three volumes of Perthane and monocrotophos spray was similar (see table). However, carbofuran and UC54229 usually were most toxic when applied at 1,000 and 500 liters. ■

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Soil and crop management

Effects of phosphorus fertilizer sources in calcareous soil

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A field experiment on calcareous silty clay soil (pH 7.7, OM 0.4% Ca 23.0 meq/100 g, Mg 13.0 meq/ 100 g, CEC 15 meq/100 g, and Olsen P 4.2 ppm) evaluated two sources of phosphate fertilizer: diammonium phosphate (DAP) and triple superphosphate (TSP). Urea was applied as a nitrogen source with TSP.

Fertilizer treatments were randomized in a complete block design with four

Effect of sources of phosphate fertilizer on plant height, tiller number, plant phosphorus concentration 30 days after transplanting, and grain yield of rice in calcareous soil in Malaysia.^a

Source of P fertilizer ^b	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	P concentration (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
None (control)	25 c	18 c	0.15 c	3.0 c
DAP	38 b	34 b	0.17 b	4.5 b
TSP	45 a	39 a	0.18 a	5.1 a
CV %	3.61	3.02	1.41	2.97

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bControl = 120 kg N/ha and no P, DAP = diammonium phosphate, TSP = triple superphosphate + urea.

replications. Nitrogen and phosphorus levels were 120 kg N/ha and 60 kg P₂O₅/ha. All of the P and half the N were broadcast and incorporated into the soil two days before IR6 seedlings were transplanted. The remaining N was topdressed at the time of panicle

initiation.

The number of tillers per hill, plant height, percent plant P concentration at 30 days after transplanting (DT), and grain yield increased significantly with the combination of urea and TSP (see table). ■

Rice germination and seedling response to oxygen in floodwater

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Germination and establishment of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) seedlings are usually less than optimum in water-saturated and flooded soils, apparently because of

a deficiency of available oxygen (O₂). This study evaluated the effect of specific O₂ levels on seedling development and identified rice cultivars that may be more tolerant of the low O₂ concentrations associated with water-saturated rice soils.

Gas flowmeters and regulators allow mixing of air and N₂ gas. Six O₂ levels — 21, 10.5, 5.3, 2.0, 1.0, and 0% (99.995% N₂ gas) — were bubbled into a transparent plastic box (36 × 28 × 9 cm deep) holding deionized water 7.5 cm

deep. Seeds of 4 rice cultivars were suspended on cheesecloth about 3 cm below the water surface. As gas of desired O₂ concentration dispersed into the box, the water circulated slowly. Water circulation plus a thin transparent polyethylene cover helped assure that O₂ concentration within each box was uniform. A YSI Model 53 O₂ meter monitored O₂ levels continuously. Seed boxes were placed in a growth chamber providing light intensity of 400 microeinsteins/m² per second, a 12-hour day,

and 27° C constant temperature. Length of coleoptile, first leaf, and primary root were measured after 1 week incubation.

Oxygen concentration had little effect on coleoptile emergence, but low O₂ levels enhanced coleoptile elongation. Maximum coleoptile length (20 mm) occurred at 0% O₂. It appears that the rice seed germinated at very low O₂ levels. Root and leaf growth were inhibited at 0% O₂, evidence that low O₂ levels can restrict rice stand establishment.

The critical O₂ concentration for maximum shoot elongation appeared to be about 5%. The critical O₂ concentration for root elongation was less evident. Roots of Labelle and Bellemont seed-

Length of rice leaf, root, and coleoptile after 1 week incubation in water saturated with 10.5% and 1% O₂ at Beaumont, Texas.

Cultivar	Difference (%) in length		
	Leaf	Root	Coleoptile
CB744	-81 ^a	-63	122
IR8	-61 ^a	-60	52
IR24	-78	-77	47 ^a
Labelle	-82	-47	135 ^a
Mars	-68	-78	93
Peta	-64	-63	62
Bellemont	-82	-35 ^a	108
Saturn	-70	-79	74
Starbonnet	-75	-90 ^a	93
TN1	-62	-40	67

^aExtremes for character.

lings reached maximum length at as low as 5% O₂. Roots of Calrose 76 and M 101 seedlings continued to increase in length at 10.5% and 21% O₂.

To help identify cultivars most tolerant of low O₂ concentrations, growth was measured for 10 cultivars in 10.5 and 1% O₂ (see table). When O₂ decreased from 10.5% to 1%, leaf length differences ranged from -61% (IR8) to -81% (CB744). Root length differences ranged from -35% (Bellemont) to -90% (Starbonnet). Coleoptile length differences ranged from 47% (IR24) to 135% (Labelle). Rice cultivars exhibited tolerance for low O₂ levels in one character, but not in the two others. ■

Late planting effects on long-duration semidwarf rices in wetland fields

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Seedling age and time of planting influence rice productivity to a great extent, particularly in short-duration, photoperiod-insensitive cultivars during the rainy season. This experiment examined the effect of late planting on growth duration and yield performance of long-duration semidwarf rice cultivars in wetland fields (20- to 50-cm water depth) during the 1977 rainy season. Materials were 15 long-duration, semidwarf rice cultivars of diverse genetical backgrounds in 2 seedling age groups, 35 days and 60 days old. The experimental design was randomized complete block with four replications. Plots (net) were 4.8 × 2.6 m with plant spacings of 20 × 15 cm and fertilizer applications of 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha.

Grain yields in both normal and late plantings did not differ significantly (see table). However, grain yields of IR32, IR34, CR1006, and IET3257 increased in the late planting. Growth duration increased in all late planted cultivars. Although growth duration increases appreciably, grain yields of normal and late plantings are comparable in long-duration semidwarf rice cultivars. ■

Grain yield and growth duration of long-duration^a semidwarf rice cultivars at normal and late planting dates during 1977 rainy season at Chinsurah, West Bengal, India.

Cultivar	Grain yield (t/ha)		Growth duration (days)	
	Normal	Late	Normal	Late
IR32	3.4	3.8	149	171
IR34	3.0	3.5	140	163
CR1006	4.0	4.3	158	180
CR1009	4.1	4.0	153	172
ET3257	3.0	3.4	149	160
ET3235	3.3	3.0	140	160
IET4087	3.1	2.7	142	157
IET2991	3.2	2.8	149	153
Pankaj (m) 107	3.8	3.4	147	161
Pankaj (m) 91	3.5	3.0	152	163
HTA448	2.8	2.6	140	167
HTA108	3.5	3.1	149	167
CNBP153-58-2	2.8	2.6	147	159
CNPB134-34-1-1	2.2	2.0	143	161
Pankaj (control)	4.4	4.3	146	164
LSD (0.05) = 0.4 t/ha	0.5	0.6		

^a Maturity of 140 days or more. Normal = 35-day-old seedlings, late = 60-day-old seedlings.

***Sesbania rostrata* green manure and rice**

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To study the effect of *Sesbania rostrata*, a tropical legume that colonizes waterlogged soils in the Senegal Valley, as green manure on rice yield, an experiment was set up in microplots (1 m² each) during the rainy season. Three treatments were used:

Sesbania rostrata green manure. Plots were sown with *S. rostrata* and kept waterlogged for 45 days (stems inoculated by spraying with a culture of *Rhizobium* strain ORS 551). Irrigation

was stopped for 7 days, and the stems of *Sesbania* were cut and plowed in. Nineteen days later, plots were fertilized with PK (17.44 g K₂HPO₄/m²), planted with 2-week-old seedlings of rice cultivar Moroberekan, and waterlogged again.

Mineral nitrogen fertilization. Plots were kept in fallow with the same water management, fertilized with PK and N (23.32 g SO₄ (NH₄)₂/m²), planted, and waterlogged.

Control. Plots were kept in fallow with the same water management, only fertilized with PK, planted, and waterlogged.

Rice was harvested when plants were 135 days old.

In the microplots which had received